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BATUMI – “A SAFE HAVEN IN THE EASTERN SHORES OF THE BLACK SEA” WITHIN THE 60S AND 70S OF THE XIX CENTURY

From the XIX century begins the aspiration of the Western states to establish intensive trade relations with the rich regions of the East through Batumi. This could be explained by the fact that Batumi was distinguished among the Black Sea coast points by its naval port conditions. In particular, Batumi possessed a cozy harbor shaped by nature. "Batumi port is the only reliable refuge for ships in the eastern part of the Black Sea." Wrote K. Marx (Batumi, Historical Essay: 1959, p. 27). However, from Batumi it is possible to establish close economic relations with almost every country of the East with the shortest and relatively safest way.

From the 50s of the XIX century, as a result of capitalist production and further development of trade, the commercial importance of Batumi as a coastal port had been increased. At that time, there was no convenient naval point in the entire eastern Black Sea coast except Batumi, where ships could enter in any weather and carry out cargo operations. The English newspaper *The Daily News* wrote in 1876: "The port of Batumi is the only safe port on the entire southeastern coast of the Black Sea to the Crimea. The water here is so deep that every large vessel can drop an anchor near the shore. Ships can be loaded and unloaded in any weather. The north and northeast winds that reach the shores of the Caucasus never blow on the shores of the Batumi port" (Chkheidze, 1974, p. 45).

In 1862, the famous Georgian writer Giorgi Eristavi stated concerning Batumi: "Numerous ships with their sails unfolded, huge vessels and small boats were sailing around" (Chkheidze, 1974, p. 47), If before only Turkish ships came here, If before only Turkish ships came here, as early as the 60s of the XIX century the merchant ships of the Russian naval and trade society, England, France, Norway, Italy, Austria, and other countries came systematically.

All this increased the cargo turnover of Batumi port. They primarily imported a variety of Manufacturing products. Manchester textiles were imported from England. Coal, iron, grain from

Russia. Sugar from France and more. In turn, they had exported timber, silk, agricultural products (Uzunadze, 1997, p. 220).

The growth of the importance of Batumi as a trade point, intensive development of navigation, gradually contributed to the improvement of Batumi city life. "Revival and growth is felt more and more in Batumi, both in terms of population and trade" Wrote the Italian consul Malmuz (Adjara in the works of foreign authors, 2010, p. 35).

As we can see, before the Russian-Turkish war of 1877-1878, Batumi was quite active and involved in trade and economic relations with European and Eastern countries. Strong European states are showing great interest in Batumi. In addition to political and economic development. It should be noted that Batumi is also starting to prosper in terms of culture, which certainly was caused by the visitors of different cultures traveling around the city. Records of foreign travelers of this time provide very interesting information about Batumi and local people as well. However, it should be noted that despite some shifts, Batumi of this period still left the impression of an Asian-type city. The Ottoman government did not take any measures to improve the city. The English newspaper "Daily News" wrote: "We cannot anticipate any substantial improvement for Batumi from the Ottomans" (Uzunadze, 1997, p. 66).

During the Ottoman occupation, Batumi found it impossible to use its great capabilities and potentials as one of the most convenient naval points on the Black Sea coast. N. Nikoladze wrote desperately: "Is not it a pitiful sight, a haven so richly endowed by nature, which must be prosperous due to commerce and trade, to look so miserable" (Uzunadze, 1997, p. 69).

The reason for this was that at first, the Ottomans were an economically underdeveloped, agrarian country where both domestic and foreign trade relations were growing at a very slow pace. In this regard, Sergei Meskhi's records about Batumi are also important. As we know, Sergei Meskhi was one of the first few people to enter Adjara after the expulsion of the Ottomans. He observes the journey to Adjara in precise detail: "Batumi is a purely Eastern, Asian city. The market, the dirt on the streets, the architecture of the buildings, the lives of the people, everything reminds you of Asia, of the East. There are only a few residences here that have little to do with Europe. These buildings are Ali-Pasha Tavdgridze's house, our consul's house, Damozhna and one or two others, which are lined up on all the shores of the sea" (Meskhi; Articles regarding Adjara).

One of the most harmful aspects of the influence that Ottoman dominance inflicted on local society, was the disruption of Georgian education centers in Adjara. Mosques and madrassas were only places that represented educational institutions. According to the data of the 90s of the XIX century, there were more than 270 madrassas in Adjara. (Akhvlediani, 1944, p. 12). Teaching in Arabic was conducted by verbal memorization and not by literacy. Georgian literacy spread relatively late as a result of the opening of Georgian schools. In March 1882, thanks to the initiative of the Society for the Promotion of Literacy among Georgians, the first Georgian school opened in Batumi.

The foundation of the Muslim religion in Adjara has fundamentally changed the status of Adjarian women in public and family life. In Adjara, as well as in Georgia as a whole, women played an important role not only in family life but also in public activities. This is an actual fact and it is proved by historical-ethnographic sources that Adjarian women often fought so fiercely against the spread of Islam and the non-Georgian rules or traditions established by the Ottomans, there were even the facts when these women came out armed with weapons. Nevertheless, women found themselves in the most disenfranchised and humiliated situation. Ethnographer and public figure Tedo Sakhokia describes the situation of a Muslim Georgian woman, recently converted to Islam as follows: "The condition of the woman here is terrible, she is locked in the house, she cannot go out in public. A diverse approach to women's rights is apparent in the rules of funeral and marriage, in how they dress. (T. Sakhokia; "Droeba").

Within 10–5 years after the liberation of Batumi from Ottoman rule, Batumi shifted its appearance significantly. Its improvement required immense attention; it took a tremendous amount of work to drain the swamps. There was built A city garden in 1881 and a seaside park in 1883. Drying up swamps, reduced the incidence of malaria.

During the Porto-Franco period, the influx of foreign travelers to Batumi increased even more. Due to the development of trade and economic relations, Batumi gradually shaped itself to become a European-type city. This is indicated in the records of many European travelers describing the life of Batumi and its population.

Famous Italian scientists – Botanist Emile Leville and anthropologist Stephan Sommier had arrived in Batumi by boat from Florence, Italy via Istanbul on the June 17th of 1890. For two months they studied and got familiarized with the nature of Georgia, the life and essence of the population. Following their purpose, they visited Batumi and its surroundings, mountainous Adjara for two months. Leville and Sommier themselves stayed in Adjara for a week. They got acquainted with the Batumi region, Adjaristskali gorge, including Goderdzi pass. Leville was a botanist by profession and the main objective of his voyage was to study the flora of Georgia and Transcaucasia. His records represent an interesting and reliable source of that time, about Batumi, Adjara, its population in particular in the 90s of the XIX century. Leville and Sommier's journey began with the introduction and description of Batumi and Adjara. Leville describes the position of Batumi, its population, its attire, its European appearance. He wrote: "While observing the locals, I presumed myself in Europe, Local Georgians and others wear a kind of long robe, which is narrow at the waist and has small pockets at the heart. All armed with daggers. Women are present without veils, as distinctive Europeans" (Adjara in the works of foreign authors: 2010, p. 37). The Italian traveler also provides a more impressive description of Adjarans: "Adjarans appear to be the most beautiful among the peoples of the Caucasus. Everyone has a perfect body and a heroic outlook. One will easily notice sharpness in walking, politeness in behavior, courage in work. Obese people are rare, almost not at all. Older men are non-less active and agile. It is a quite wonderful picture when an Adjarian man with his beautiful clothes sits on a

horse. All are armed as if all they think of is nothing more than fight and death" (Kakhidze, 2010, p. 84).

According to the records of Italian travelers, in the XIX century, Adjara with the local people was advanced culturally and economically. Trade and economic relations with various European countries have contributed to the active influx of Western culture and Western civilization in Adjara, most specifically in Batumi and its suburbs.

As it is certain from the history of Batumi, at the turn of the XIX-XX centuries there were consulates of seventeen countries in the city: These were Austria-Hungary, Prussia (Germany), North America, France, Denmark, Italy, Belgium, the Ottoman Empire, Persia, Japan, Britain, Sweden, Norway, and so on. (Bagrationi, 2010, p. 75). Batumi was formally declared as Porto-Franco on October 29, 1878, and operated until June 27, 1886. This form of administration has made life within the city significantly more expensive.

In 1880, German merchants arrived in Batumi: Richter, Neumann and Prechder. They purchased land in the city and constructed several residences. Documentary materials show that in 1884 a German individual named Dorner built a bath in Batumi, which was designed and coated with European style. In 1885, the German traveler Gottfried Herman arrived in Batumi. Herman's impressions about Batumi are quite impressive. Herman's impressions about Batumi are quite informative. As we read, he despised the climate of Batumi, frequent rain showers, and clogged muddy streets. According to him, the city was being reconstructed. Houses, hotels, shops, and more were being built. The port was working at full capacity. By 1882 the number of German individuals in the city was 145, and by 1887 it was 200 individuals, and by 1897 it was 300 individuals. Most of the Germans living in the city were devotees of various specialties. Particularly, engineers, teachers, artists, merchants, workers and more. The Germans are mentioned in the report card of the military governor of the Batumi district, sent to the Chancellery of the Governor-General of the Caucasus in 1887, Where the Germans are characterized as a people loyal to the Russian state. Besides, it is indicated that they are people of the necessary profession and with their culture they are much higher than other foreign population of Batumi (Gogolishvili, 2019, p. 95).

As we have already mentioned, Batumi is becoming a very progressive city for this period and this progress was determined by its geopolitical location. A travel novel by Austrian couple, Arthur Gundaccar von Suttner and Berta Suttner, translated into Georgian in 2007 by Rusudan Gvinepadze, contains very interesting information about the history of Batumi during this period. The rapid pace of trade and economic development of Batumi is well reflected in the work of Arthur Suttner. During Arthur Suttner's activity in Georgia, Batumi was literally changing and evolving, not only statistically, but also architecturally, demographically, ethnically, confessionally, and economically. Since it has located in neutral territory, trade relations with foreign countries flourished so much that some powerful countries were obliged to open consulates while their family members enjoyed the opportunity to enjoy a monotonous life through gatherings at the governor's home" (Adjara in the works of foreign authors, 2020, p. 42).

Arthur Suttner is also interested in the ethnic composition of the region, including people of Abkhazian, Greek and Armenian descent. Based on historical sources, we can say that since the 1980s, when Batumi officially became part of Russia with the status of Porto-Franco, this part of the Black Sea coast has rapidly developed into a polyethnic city, which at the dawn of capitalist relations was a result of growing trade and economic relationship. There are many records of foreign authors on Batumi of this period, among which the journey of the Norwegian novelist, Nobel Laureate Knut Hamsun to the Caucasus is exceptional. Knut Hamsun traveled to Russia and Georgia in September 1899. Several pages of his work are committed to Batumi and its surroundings. Hamsun wrote: "There are fifty inhabitants in Batumi or a little more, it looks like Tiflis and Baku. There are large, modern whitewashed houses and small stone buildings from the time of Turkish rule. The streets are wide but unpaved, people and carriages walk directly in the sand. There are many ships in the port, starting with the small sailing boats that came here from the southern cities, ending with the large ships of Alexandria and Marseilles. The city is located in swampy and unhealthy places but it's surrounded by forests, fertile lands with cornfields, and vineyards. The ruins of a castle can be observed from the hills covered with thorns" (Tunadze, 2010, p. 127).

Along with the fact that Batumi has become a major export point, Rothschild, Mantashev, Nobel, and other monopolistic associations have been firmly established in the city. They controlled the technically well-equipped enterprises of that time, which mainly defined the commercial profile of Batumi district.

The most notable of them is the Rothschild factory and its French director Gion, who hired only Georgian individuals. He believed that "Georgians are conscientious workers and do the job entrusted to them in a timely manner". That was why the workers at the Rothschild factory were Georgians. He declared: "The Russians are distinguished by a superficial attitude to the case". Because of this, French Gion was shunned by the leadership of the Batumi district. During a meeting with the military governor of the Batumi district, Russian officials attacked Georgians and called them robbers and rioters. They demanded a reduction in the number of Georgian workers in factories, instructing directors to reduce Georgians and hire only Russians instead. Gion harshly opposed such chauvinist actions of the government and criticized their actions. (Gogolishvili, 2019, p. 30, 35).

As we can see, the foreigners who managed their business on the territory of Batumi had great respect for the local population, their culture, and their values. Despite the substantial conflict, the executive of the Rothschild factory supported Georgian workers and respected their rights.

Although Adjara with its natural wealth, mild climate, geostrategic location with sea resources has attracted many foreigners since ancient times, until the XIX century here were mainly rural and community-type settlements. Even during the Ottoman rule, new types of urban settlements were gradually developing, barter exchange was being revived, and economic

relations with various regions were expanding. In this regard, Batumi was the most advanced, which took an honorable place among the various cities of the Black Sea (Sichinava, 1958, p. 25).

Prominent patronage of the Christian population by the King-Emperor during the Russo-Ottoman Wars led to the increased interest of people living in the Ottoman Empire (Such as Greeks, Armenians, Kurds, and others) toward Georgia, including the Batumi region. The expansion of the Batumi port and the development of navigation gradually caused the revival of the city's trade and economic relations with neighboring countries, which led to an increase in its importance. Its effect also was the raised interest of foreign merchants, industrialists, and workers in Batumi. The opening of the shipping line gave a wide profile to the trade through Batumi.

During the transition period, rapid demographic growth was observed in the city of Batumi. As the English Consul in Anatolia V.J. Palgrev informs us: In 1872, 4,970 individuals lived in the city, 4,500 Muslims, 350 Greeks, and 120 Armenians (Varshanidze, Kakhidze, 1960, p. 287).

After the end of the Russo-Turkish war of 1877-78, the majority of the population of Batumi have departed. Most of the Ottoman bondmen left the city. By 1880 the population of the city had increased to four thousand, and by 1882 there were 8671 people living in Batumi. As a result, Batumi became a multi-ethnic city.

According to the census of 1882, the ethnic composition of the population of Batumi formed the following picture: the population was mainly Georgians, Armenians, Greeks and Russians, in addition, the European and American population began to enter Batumi, which was followed by the opening of foreign consulates in Batumi. (Varshanidze, Kakhidze. Imperial view of the demographic situation in Batumi in the last quarter of the XIX century and its modern analogies, p. 287). By 1882, 316 Armenian Catholics and 178 Latin Catholics lived in Batumi. If we look at the statistics we will see that the number of Catholics in Batumi is gradually increasing. The number of Catholics in Batumi by 1886 is as follows: Polish Catholic – 250, German Catholic – 111, French Catholic – 67. According to the data of 1890, the number of Catholics in Batumi increases even more. The number of Latin Catholics reaches 1151, while the number of Armenian Catholics has increased to 508 (Varshanidze, 2006).

It should be noted that in addition to Latin Catholics, the number of Georgian Catholics was quite large in the Batumi region. This is evidenced by Zakaria Chichinadze's article, where he states: "Catholicism has increased in Batumi so that in a short period the number of Georgian Catholics rose to several thousand people. The local Catholics, those who came temporarily from here and there, were busy with trading and barter. The number of such Catholics almost totally consisted of the Georgian Catholic families. They were and still are Georgian speakers (Komakhidze, 1999, p. 21).

These processes contributed to the development of Batumi as a European city, and at the end of the XIX century as the initiative of Georgian Catholics (Zubalashvili brothers) the

construction of the first monumental Catholic church launched in Batumi. As we have already mentioned, Catholics have lived in Batumi since ancient times. Nevertheless, until the first half of the XIX century, there was only one Catholic Church here. This church was a Catholic chapel of the Armenian rule.

As a result of the Russo-Turkish War, after the return of Adjara, the number of Georgian Catholics in the Batumi district increased to several thousand. The military road was built and Batumi was connected to Akhaltsikhe from the side of mountainous Adjara. As an important port city related to Europe and Constantinople, a Georgian Catholic Church of the Immaculate Conception of the Blessed Virgin Mary was actively functioning in Batumi. It was founded by a compassionate patriot – Petre Kharischarishvili. All this led to the aspiration of Georgian Catholics to Batumi. Towards Batumi. At that time it was the only European city in Georgia and Georgian Catholics pursued trade and handicrafts here.

All Georgian Catholics belonged to the Latin rule. The growth of the parish put the issue of building a new temple on the agenda. There were many consulates of European Catholic countries in Batumi at that time. Father Anselmo Modzgvishvili, a Latin Catholic priest in Batumi, with the help of consulates, received permission from the Russian emperor to build a church. Part of the site for the church was set aside by the city government, and part was purchased at the expense of the parish, and the foundation of the church was laid on April 12, 1897. The church was built in the name of the Blessed Virgin Mary, its construction was fully funded by the Georgian Catholic oil magnate Stefane Zubalashvili. Stephen was also supported by his brothers. Because of this, the name of the temple was closely connected with the Zubalashvili brothers and their charitable activities. According to legend, their mother had a long desire to build a Catholic church in Batumi, and the brothers also built this church to commemorate her soul. This is evidenced by the marble stones on both sides of the main entrance with Georgian and French construction inscriptions, which indicates that the temple was built by Stephen Zubalashvili, son of Constantine, "for the salvation of the souls of his parents and brothers and sisters".

Along with Stefanie Zubalashvili, Father Anselmo Mghebrishvili also hugely contributed to the construction of the church. The whole challenge of the construction fell on his shoulders. Father Anselmo Mghebrishvili could not attend the blessing of the church due to a serious illness. The church was consecrated on May 5, 1903, by Bishop Edward Baron Rope who specially arrived in Batumi. Unfortunately, the events which took place in the country in the 1930s, caused the Catholic Cathedral like other temples, to lose its function. It survived the demolition, An archive was placed in it first, and then a high-voltage laboratory, which severely damaged the interior of the temple. Therefore, in the 1980s, when the issue of opening a cultural center in the building arose, an absolute restoration became necessary. Artists led by Amiran Goglidze worked on the restoration of the wall painting washed away by rainwater.

After the restoration, the building was transferred to the Ministry of Culture of Adjara and an art center was opened in it. In 1989, the Catholicos-Patriarch of All Georgia Ilia II and members of the Holy Synod arrived in Batumi, who consecrated the temple orthodoxly and held a solemn, large-scale baptism.

Thus, if we look closely at the statistics, it becomes clear to the reader that by the end of the XIX century the number of Catholics in the city of Batumi and its neighborhoods had increased considerably. They were actively involved in the city life of Batumi. It was their growth and activity that led us to the logical conclusion that the first Catholic church in Batumi was built on the initiative of Georgian Catholics in Batumi.

Based on these facts, we can confidently talk about the formation of Batumi as a prosperous, western-type city in the last quarter of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century. If we take a good look at the existing accounts about Batumi, we will see that despite centuries of Ottoman rule and even in the process of being part of the Ottoman Empire, the Ottomans were not able to turn Batumi into an integral part of the Eastern world.

Relations with Europe began through Russia in the last quarter of the 19th century. We mean that the same "Sixtians", or "Tergdaleulis", reached European civilization through Russia. German literature translated into Russian raised the national self-consciousness of Georgians to some extent. Already in the early twentieth century, "Tsisferkantsels" began to care not only about relations with modern Europe but also about the returning of Georgian culture to the Western civilization.

Dr. Adrian Briscu of Carl University in Prague explains in his paper "So Far and Still So Close, the Face of Europe in Georgia": In the second half of the 19th century, the image of Europe for Georgians was defined by three closely related representations: Europe as a geopolitical space, Europe as a model of political, social and economic progress, Europe as the cradle of modern civilization. These performances had a rather Ambiguous impact on the history of Georgia, starting with the national movement that emerged in the second half of the 19th century, continuing with the creation of the first Georgian state after the overthrow of Tsarist Russia and ending with the collapse of the Soviet Union. Despite such doubtfulness, all this time in Georgia, there has been a claim that the country was part of Europe because it was associated with the desire for progress and a better future (Briscu, 2017, p. 7).

As Reinhart Kozelek demonstrated, the notion of the future in modern times is an expression of a philosophy of progress that combines prophecy and political structure with rational predictions and expectations of salvation. The image of Europe, loaded with anticipation of the future, acted as a catalyst in Georgia, as it bridged the "horizon of promise" and created a new "space of expectation".

Since the beginning of the XX century, the economic advancement of Batumi has been conditioned by the search for the shortest way to transport Baku oil abroad. Batumi port turned out to be the shortest way, although there were options for other ports, but Batumi surpassed everyone. Along with dozens of export firms, the largest, monopolistic oil firms (Rothschild,

Nobel, Mantashev) were firmly established, and with vigorous operations in a favorable market environment, they became magnates of oil export. They also controlled the operation of solid, technically well-equipped oil-exporting enterprises here which became the leading industry in the entire Western Caucasus and defined the commercial life profile of the city itself. Over time, the new function of Batumi contributed to the economic development of the city. It is noteworthy, however, that workers' rights were severely restricted, strikes were frequent due to inadequate pay. If we take into account, the fact that by this time Batumi "stood above all the cities of the Caucasus in terms of the cost of living and even in Russia it was second only to the capital. "All this was happening at a time when the export of oil products and the oil business in Batumi was experiencing its "golden age" (Gogolishvili, 2019, p. 166).

The ongoing processes in the early twentieth century have shown that despite some restrictions, local workers were very aware of their rights and had an appropriate response, it can even be said that by this time it spoke of a high level of public thinking. At the same time, it should be noted that since the second half of 1904, the entrepreneurs operating in Batumi, foreign shipping companies have been constantly appealing to the authorities, urging them to take decisive measures. Diplomatic service also intervened in the campaign. The British consul P. Stevens in January 1905 repeatedly asked the governor for help in resolving the workers' issue. The current crisis has hindered the conduct of shipping operations. "British ships stay in port for weeks without doing any actual work" (Gogolishvili, 2019, p. 174).

Batumi back then had undergone the process of transformation into a multi-ethnic community. As the population grew, so did the development of cultural institutions in the city. It was essential to establish new educational institutions. Schools were opened, a theater with a very active troupe led performances. Foreign actors came to the Batumi Theater. Internationally recognized singers often visited Batumi. Concerts were performed. The growth of the theatrical troupe required the allocation of a new building for the theater. We will talk about the opening of schools in Batumi in more detail in the following sections, which will be dedicated to the foundation of the first centers of Western education in southwestern Georgia during our research period.

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